

SHORT-TERM SCINTILLATION PREDICTION FOR THE BRAZILIAN SOUTHEAST USING MACHINE LEARNING

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A data-oriented approach using machine learning is employed for the short-term, 15-minute, scintillation prediction over Brazil. It aims to provide a warning about the percentage of the map area in Brazil affected by moderate-strong ionospheric scintillation, and also the percentage of the corresponding probability map area. For this study, a dataset was generated providing a two-dimensional time series of amplitude scintillation maps [2], comprehending 125 consecutive nights, from 08/28/2014 to 12/30/2014, during the Solar Maximum of 2014 with a total of 4,375 scintillation maps. A set of 35 maps were generated for each night, being the first map for 20:30 UT and the last map for 05:00 UT. Each map integrates 30 minutes of data, using 29 minutes of a priori data and a sliding window allows an overlap of 15 minutes to provide a smooth transition between consecutive maps. A second dataset was created deriving the corresponding probability of scintillation occurrence maps [3] from each scintillation map of the former dataset. The time series of maps for each night allows to follow the evolution of the scintillation over the Brazilian territory. The GNSS amplitude scintillation data was obtained from two ionospheric monitoring networks, LISN [4], which covers most of South America, and INCT [5] stations, covering only the Brazilian territory. LISN receivers are only compatible with GPS and SBAS satellites, while INCT receivers are multi-constellation. These networks provided a total of 46 ionospheric monitoring stations. In order to answer how large is the area affected by scintillation, the two-dimensional time series of amplitude scintillation maps was reduced to a one-dimensional time series given by the percentage of the map area affected by moderate-strong amplitude scintillation (S4 values above 0.5). This study also generated the corresponding maps of probability of occurrence. This new type of map considers the azimuthal and elevation angles of each satellite-station link given by ephemeris data to calculate such probability. The same reduction of dimensionality is done for the corresponding moderate-strong probability maps, resulting in another one-dimensional time series of the percentage of the probability map area affected by moderate-strong scintillation. Also, to have a better identification of the area that will undergo scintillation, the considered map was divided into 4 quadrants, and thus the time series of the amplitude scintillation allows to derive 4 time series given by the corresponding percentage of area with moderate-strong scintillation for each quadrant (Figure 1). In addition, the same dimensionality reduction is done for the corresponding moderate-strong probability maps, resulting in 4 time series given by the percentage of area with the probability of moderate-strong scintillation above zero for each quadrant (Figure 2). The prediction then yields, for each night interval, a percentage of the area of the map/quadrant affected by moderate-strong amplitude scintillation, either considering amplitude scintillation maps/quadrants or the derived probability maps/quadrants. The prediction of these derived one-dimensional time series can be modeled as a supervised learning problem, allowing the use of standard linear or nonlinear machine learning algorithms. However, the time series needs to be partitioned, defining former instances of the time series as predictive variables, while defining latter instances as variables to be predicted. For instance, this may be achieved using the area of the previous time step as input and the corresponding area of the next time step as the output, assuming a temporal dependency. In addition, more input variables were used, as the mean area value of the previous 3 nights. The prediction for time (t) employs the preceding variables in 15-minute intervals of the same night. Thus, prediction of the percentage of map area for time (t) uses as predictive variables the percentages of map area of the 3 preceding times, i.e. (t - 3), (t - 2), and (t - 1). Furthermore, the prediction is enhanced adding the mean of the exogenous variable F10.7 (solar flux) of the previous 3 nights as a further predictive variable. Data-oriented machine learning algorithms are trained from known historical data, thus using samples of the predictive variables and of the target variable to be predicted, the percentage of the map area undergoing moderate-strong scintillation. Here, the proposed predictive model is implemented by an ensemble of parallel decision trees, the eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost). However, instead of deriving a predictive model for all the duration of the night, predictions are made for

the period of 21:15-05:00 UT, which is divided into 32 intervals of 15 minutes. Therefore, XGBoost derives a set of 32 predictive models for each night, since each model needs the area values for the previous three discrete times. In this initial implementation, the training process does not use autoregression, i.e. does not include the previous predictions into the training data, but real data instead. A walk-forward validation scheme was employed for the partitioning of the available data into training and test sets for the 32 models. Walk-forward is a time-series cross-validation scheme usually employed for data that is ordered in time. Data is usually split into training, validation, and test sets, but here a different data partitioning is employed due to the scarce amount of data related to moderate-strong scintillation occurrences. As new data becomes available for following nights, such data is included in the training set, and prediction is then performed using the data from all the preceding nights for each time interval. This allows the update of the set of models as new real data is made available in the acquisition process. A baseline model, the persistence model (PM), was chosen as a reference model in order to compare its predictions to those given by XGBoost. The PM uses the percentage of map area at the current time step (t) as the predicted percentage of map area at the next time step ($t+1$), a reasonable assumption, since the prediction time is only 15 minutes. The employed metrics are the RMSE and the Pearson's correlation coefficient, calculated from the prediction error of the percentage of map area presenting moderate-strong scintillation for each night interval. Using the time series obtained from the scintillation maps, the RMSE values for XGBoost were much lower for all 4 quadrants than for PM, while average correlation for all quadrants was 0.86 for XGBoost and 0.41 for PM. Considering the 2nd quadrant (Brazilian Southeast), more affected by scintillation, the correlation was similar, 0.87 for XGBoost and 0.49 for PM. For the corresponding maps of probability of occurrence, RMSE values for XGBoost were also consistently lower for all 4 quadrants than for PM, while average correlation for all quadrants was 0.94 for XGBoost and 0.65 for PM. Considering the 2nd quadrant, correlation was similar, 0.95 for XGBoost and 0.64 for PM. Such results demonstrate the better monitoring and predictions provided by the probability maps for amplitude scintillation. The proposed approach shows the feasibility of predicting moderate-strong scintillation with antecedence of 15 minutes for each quadrant and for each of the 32-night intervals, thus allowing to predict the evolution of the ionospheric scintillation over the Brazilian territory. The prediction with antecedence up to one hour is underway.

Figure 1 – Examples of amplitude scintillation maps (left panel), and the corresponding 4 quadrants showing moderate-strong scintillation, i.e. S4 above 0.5.

Source: Martinon (2024).

Figure 2 – Examples of moderate-strong amplitude probability maps (left panel), and the corresponding 4 quadrants (right panel), showing probabilities above zero.

Source: Martinon (2024)

Keywords: ionospheric scintillation prediction; machine learning; XGBoost; time series prediction.

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